

Evaluation of Domestic Field Study using CIPP Model: Analytical Study of Indonesian RIDU

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November , 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Domestic Field Study, Indonesian RIDU, CIPP Model, Program Evaluation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5678997</p>	<p><i>Domestic Field Study is a program created to provide additional knowledge and competence of students at Republic of Indonesia Defense University(RIDU) in carrying out daily activities after they graduate. The purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of the Domestic Field Study (KKDN) program. This study uses the CIPP evaluation approach developed by Stufflebeam. In the context evaluation stage, this study found that RIDU had carried out and prepared all its infrastructure very well to support this program. From the component inputs, this program has also clearly prepared a very adequate support capacity. For the component evaluation process, although in general it has been going well, there still needs to be improvements, especially the involvement of students in the process of independent activities. Meanwhile, for the evaluation of component products, this program requires improvements, especially in terms of output where the research results are in the form of publication of articles and books. In general, the Domestic Field Study program is evaluated to be feasible to be continued with minor improvements, especially in process and product components.</i></p>

Introduction

Community service is a part of the academic culture of higher education institutions in Indonesia. It is implemented with the expertise and scientific autonomy of the academic community as well as the socio-cultural conditions of the community. The implementation of community service is also an opportunity for students to practice their knowledge and skills in order to make a positive and constructive contribution to society, nation and state. The form of community service is through Actual Work Lectures or often called *KuliahKerjaNyata*(KKN).

KKN activities within Republic of Indonesia Defense University (RIDU) are better known as Work Lectures or Field Study. For this reason, the RIDU has developed Field Study activities that do not only contain work activities of the RIDU academic community but also a series of interdisciplinary integrative activities that are strategically packaged to solve problems completely. This program is also implemented with the community by involving other relevant stakeholders. In this case, students are expected to be able to become solution developers, motivators, and facilitators in the process of problem solving and development in the community. The presence of students as state defense intellectuals is expected to be able to develop themselves as prospective leaders and agents of change who are intelligent and able to help solve problems faced by their community. There are two forms of KKN which is *KuliahKerjaLuar Negeri* (KKLN) which is conducted in a foreign country and *KuliahKerjaDalam Negeri* (KKDN) which is implemented domestically.

KKDN activities at RIDU are carried out in 34 provinces alternately. While KKDN activities have been organized by RIDU since 2010, there are still in fact many various obstacles and limitations. Communities who are the objects and locations of KKDN activities convey various inputs so that the KKDN program can sustain and have better coverage. In the KKDN program, students are required to conduct research in accordance with the study program and the results of the research are then held in seminars. Since 2010, the KKDN program has been implemented 10 times according to the academic year. Initially, the RIDU KKDN was carried out in the outer islands and the outermost border of the Indonesian state. From the first batch or cohort of the RIDU in 2010 to the sixth batch in 2016, the KKDN implementation was held in the outermost and border areas. Since about 2017, the form of KKDN is no longer focused on border areas but to the centers or provincial areas that are being studied according to their field of study.

Various research projects have been conducted in regard to implementation of the Student Study Service program (Widyaputra, 2018; Anwas, 2011). Related to the implementation of an education, of course, it is necessary to evaluate the education program implemented. The purpose of the program evaluation is to improve the quality of education from year to year so that higher education institutions can make a positive contribution to the nation and state and society.

From the beginning until now, there has never been a program evaluation of KKDN program organized by RIDU in a comprehensive and in-depth manner, both in terms of process, product and subject. Therefore, research on the evaluation of the KKDN program carried out by the Faculties and Study Programs at RIDU needs to be carried out in order to assess the effectiveness of the KKDN program organizers.

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of the basic needs (needs assessment), legal basis, goals and objectives of the KKDN program organized by the Faculties and Study Programs at the RIDU. In addition, this study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the planning and preparation of the organizing organization regarding program activities, which include human resource support, infrastructure, and the budget required by the Faculties and Study Programs that organize KKDN.

Program Evaluation

Evaluation Concepts

Evaluation is the provision of information that can be used as consideration in making decisions (Stufflebeam & Zhang, 2017). Evaluation activities are activities in determining the value (worth) or service (merit) of an evaluation object (Fitzpatrick, Sanders, & Worthen, 2010). Wholey, Hatry, & Newcomer (2010) states that value evaluation is measured in the strength of the evidence generated in the credibility of the evaluation to policy makers, managers, and other users in using evaluation information to improve policies and programs. Dočekal and Dvořáková (2015) stated that evaluation is a very complex process, where each phase is interrelated with each other, therefore it is not enough to carry out evaluation only during the learning process. Evaluation is transdisciplinary because it is an essential element in other academic disciplines, as a tool that distinguishes science from pseudo-disciplines (Wirawan, 2016). From several theories and concepts of evaluation and the opinions of experts above and other literature, a general understanding of evaluation can be drawn, namely that evaluation is an integral part of an activity intended to improve the implementation of activities or to provide information related to the process and results of these activities so that a decision can be made about the feasibility, benefits and value of the activity. Evaluation is an activity that includes systematic and continuous measurement and assessment to determine the quality of something, based on certain considerations and criteria in order to make a decision. Evaluation is a systematic process in selecting, collecting, analysing, and providing information that is carried out through measurement and assessment to make the right decision on a phenomenon, by comparing the results with the evaluation criteria, so that it can be determined that the object being evaluated is of value or benefit to the community. organization. In general, evaluation is a systemic process to determine the level of success of a program.

Program Concepts

A program is a plan that involves various units that contain policies and a series of activities that must be carried out within a certain period of time (Ananda & Rafida, 2017). According to Arikunto and Jabar (2018) the program can be called the realization of the policy. Program is anything that someone tries to do with the hope that it will bring results or influence (Tayibnaxis, 2018). Based on the opinion of experts about the program, it can be redefined that the program is the realization of policies that involve the complexity of people, organizations, management, and use of resources as a whole through continuous efforts and in a relatively long time in a multicultural environment to achieve certain results. In solving problems felt by the organization, carried out in a planned and organized manner, guided by the rules and procedures, to achieve a goal or maximum result for the organization. Thus, a complete understanding of the program can be taken, namely an activity that is managed carefully and together by using existing resources and involving a group of people in order to achieve a goal effectively and oriented to certain policies.

Program Evaluation

Program evaluation according to Spaulding (2013) explains that program evaluation is carried out for decision-making purposes, in general from program evaluation it can be determined the meaning of a program, the results are in the form of recommendations for improvement so that success can be achieved. Chen (2005) also stated that "Program evaluation is defined as the application of evaluation approaches techniques, and knowledge to systematically assess and improve the planning, implementation, and effectiveness of programs".

Program evaluation is a process of providing information that can be used as consideration for determining prices and services from the objectives to be achieved, design, implementation and impact to assist accountability and increase understanding of the phenomena of a program (Widoyoko, 2016). Program evaluation is the application of evaluation approaches, techniques and knowledge to assess systematically to improve program planning, implementation, and effectiveness. Program evaluation is part of the management in an organization's management system that is oriented towards implementing policies that have been designed by an organization through programs.

According to Arikunto (2009) program evaluation is an effort to determine the level of implementation of a policy carefully by knowing the effectiveness of each of its components. Program evaluation is an activity that is included in the management agenda of an organization and becomes a component in the system.

Wirawan(2016) explained that program evaluation efforts include a systematic method for collecting, analysing and using information to answer basic questions about the program. Sudjana(2006) states that program evaluation is a systematic activity to collect, process, analyse, and present data as input for decision making. Program evaluation is an activity that is intended to find out how high the level of success of the planned activities is(Arikunto & Jabar, 2018). Program evaluation is a systematic process, it is necessary to share information or data regarding the object being evaluated(Ananda & Rafida, 2017). The decision placement process is based on a comparison of the observed data using certain standardized standards. Program evaluation is used as a social research procedure that systematically investigates the effectiveness of social intervention programs adapted to political organizational environments and designed to inform social action by improving social conditions (Robert and Gilbert, 2009).

This form is focused on activities, instructor performance, facilities, and materials. This form can be applied to various educational situations and areas of satisfaction(Darodjat & M, 2015). The program is an integral part of policy. Policy evaluation research aims to produce recommendations that form the basis for policy formulation, support policy implementation or to determine the performance and impact of policies(Mulyatiningsih, 2014).

From various explanations, it can be understood that program evaluation is a unit or unit of activity that aims to collect information on the realization or implementation of a policy, takes place in a continuous process, and occurs in an organization that involves a group of people for decision making. Program evaluation aims to determine the achievement of program objectives that have been implemented. The benefits of program evaluation can be in the form of discontinuing the program, revising the program, continuing the program, and disseminating the program. In program evaluation, the implementer (evaluator) wants to know how high the quality or condition of something is because of program implementation after the data has been collected compared to certain criteria or standards. In program evaluation, the executor (evaluator) wants to know the level of achievement of the program, and if the objectives have not been achieved, the executor (evaluator) wants to know the location of the shortcomings and why. The results are used to determine follow-up or decisions to be taken. In program evaluation activities, indicators are instructions to determine the success or failure of an activity.

Program Evaluation Methods

The program evaluation model is quite varied. Of all the existing models, the model that will be selected is the CIPP Evaluation Model(Stufflebeam, 2002). Stufflebeam defines evaluation as a process of delineating, observing, and providing useful information to assess decision-making alternatives. Stufflebeam& Zhang (2017)explained that "CIPP evaluation model is designed to systematically guide both evaluators and stakeholders in posing relevant questions and conducting assessments at the beginning of a project (Context and Input evaluation) while it is in progress (Input and Process evaluation) and its end (Product evaluation). This means that the CIPP evaluation model is designed systematically as a guide for evaluators and stakeholders in asking relevant questions and conducting an initial project assessment (context and evaluation input), while it is ongoing (Input and process) and at the end (Product).

The CIPP model was chosen from other models because Stufflebeam provides a more complete modeling framework and can map from the early stages of the environment, inputs or inputs, the process of a series of activities and KKDN programs as well as the final product or outcome issued from a program. Based on this description, the researcher chose the CIPP Program Evaluation model as anevaluativeresearch.

Methods

This research activity is planned at the RIDU specifically the Faculty of Defense Strategy, at the Faculty of Defense Management, and Faculty of Defense Technology, in the Sentul Bogor and SalembaMatraman areas, Jakarta. Qualitative research that uses social data collected through interactions with people related to the social situation being studied. In this program evaluation research, the social situation in question is the Faculty of Defense Strategy, the Faculty of Defense Management, and the Faculty of Defense Technology which implements the KKDN. The selection of triangulation subjects or information planned by policy makers from the Echelon I and Echelon II levels of the Defense University located on the Sentul campus and Salemba campus.

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach in the sense that research that aims to provide an overview of natural social phenomena by processing data that is narrative and does not use statistical techniques

Instruments

How to optimally improve the smooth achievement of the goals of the KKDN program? Are the available facilities able to serve the needs of each faculty and those who implement the KKDN? Is there an increase in competence according to each discipline? How do students respond to the KKDN program implemented? How about the time for KKDN for 5 to 7 days is it enough or does it still need to be added?

Informants or resource persons in this study are the parties providing information according to the data needed in the research and are trusted personnel who know various things related to the implementation of the KKDN Program including planning, implementation, and program results. The parties who became the informants of this research included students, alumni, lecturers, education staff, university management, faculty management, and study program management within the Defense University. Informant profile is defined as the following description:

1. Student

The students who were selected as informants in this study were RIDU students who had already participated in the KKDN program. Students represent their class in the study program and include all Study Programs that implement the KKDN Program in 2017, 2018, and 2019. The selection of students is based on an appointment from the Secretary of the Study Program.

2. Alumni

Alumni selected as informants in this study are RIDU alumni who have participated in the KKDN program. There are 10 alumni whose appointments are made randomly but are believed to know various information related to the implementation of the Defense University Student KKDN, especially those related to alumni.

3. Lecturer

The lecturers who were selected as informants in this study were Permanent Lecturers of the Defense University, both those who had or had never participated in the KKDN program and were trusted to know various things related to the implementation of the Defense University Student KKDN program.

4. Support staff

Supporting staff or education staff who became informants in this study were personnel who had and also never participated in the KKDN program but were trusted to know various things related to the implementation of the Defense University Student KKDN Program.

5. University Management

University management who became informants in this study were related officials including the Chancellor, Vice Chancellor, Chair of the Institute, and Head of Bureau and elements under these officials who knew about the implementation of the KKDN program for RIDU students.

6. Faculty Management

Faculty management who became informants in this study were officials within the Faculty including the Dean or Deputy Dean who knew the implementation of the Defense University Student KKDN program.

7. Study Program Management

The Management of the Study Program who became informants in this study were the Secretary of the Study Program who knew about the implementation of the Defense University Student KKDN program.

Results and Discussion

Context Evaluation

Context evaluation in this study was conducted to see and evaluate the legal basis or policy basis, needs assessment, goals and objectives of the KKDN. Table 1 displays research results on the Context phase.

Table 1. Context Phase Research Results

Code	Aspect	Standard	Results
C-1	Legal Basis	There is a legal basis that forms the basis for implementing the Domestic Field Study (KKDN) program.	Documentation Available, namely Law 20 of 2003 on National Education System, Law No 12 of 2012 on Higher Education, Presidential Regulation No 5 Year 2011 on Defense University, Defense University Working Program, Rector Regulations No 21 Year 2014. Field Observation shows every activity is based on the same legal basis. Interview results shows that all stakeholders confirm their knowledge on this legal basis
C-2	Needs Assessment	There is a significant Need Assessment related to the need for the implementation of the Domestic Field Study program (KKDN) which is carried out every year.	Documentation of Activity Report related to need assessment is available. Also final report showing feedback from the society where the program is implemented is also available. Field Observation shows that all stakeholders use needs assessment to plan the program Interview results shows that all stakeholders confirm their knowledge of implemented of needs assessment.
C-3	Goals	The program has a goal that will have a good impact on the development of the area that is the object of the implementation of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN).	Documentation shows that all program participants were carried out in accordance with the original purpose of this program being launched. Interview results shows that all stakeholders confirm their knowledge of the original goals of the program.
C-4	Objectives	Having the right target as evidenced by an analysis of the needs of the areas that will be used as the object of the implementation of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN).	Documentation shows that objectives of this program is students in the 2 nd semester in RIDU. Interview results shows that all stakeholders confirm their knowledge on the objectives of the program.

Input Evaluation

Input evaluation results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Input Phase Research Results

Code	Aspect	Standard	Results
I-1	Organization Structure	Having a complete organizational structure starting from the leadership element as a policy maker to implementing activities.	Documentation in the form of activity reports shows that every year, the implementation of Domestic Field Study involves all stakeholders who have an interest in the successful implementation of activities and is incorporated into the inherent organizational structure and ad-hoc organizational structure. Field Observation shows involvement of all RIDU stakeholders in the implementation of the Domestic Work Lecture program and incorporated into the organizational structure attached to positions and ad-hoc committees. The data obtained confirms that each stakeholder in this program is included in the organizational structure, whether it is attached to the position held so far or the ad-hoc committee that was arranged when the program was implemented.
I-2	Program Plan	The program is carried out by making all the needs that will be carried out during the program.	Documentation shows the existence of a very comprehensive planning starting from the legal basis, activity plans, resources involved, facilities and infrastructure needed and also the availability of a budget that supports the implementation. Field observation found that the planning process was carried out through meetings conducted by the head of the university, the head of the faculty and also the head of the study program as the field executor of the activity. Discussions in the meeting confirmed the results of the documentation, which mostly included program planning related to policies, facilities needed and also funding for activities. Interview results shows that each stakeholder in this program as a whole understands and is able to practice the program plan that will be carried out based on the main tasks and functions of each.
I-3	Activity Strategy	Curriculum and teaching materials are determined using the KKNI curriculum that has been provided by the Rector and refers to the Graduate Competency Standards (SKL) and Competency-Based Curriculum (KBK) but implementing agencies can adjust especially for skills for which there is no KKNI standard. Soft skills curriculum is given to students for at least 25 hours.	Documentation shows that the strategy for the Domestic Field Study program (KKDN) begins by preparing raw input from students as implementers of the activity and also instrumental input that functions as a supporter of these activities including supervisors, organizers, resource persons, facilities needed and also the budget. Field observation shows in the concept of activity strategy, RIDU carries out various meetings and discussions both formally and informally with all parties involved from planning to implementation. Interview results shows that all stakeholder understand each function and able to support the strategy as a whole.
I-4	Curriculum	The standard of facilities and infrastructure is determined by the	Documentation shows there is a curriculum set as a guide for the implementation of this KKDN program including academic calendar and specific implementation guides.

		Rector in the form of 1) theory and practice study room, 2) practical room and equipment in accordance with the field of expertise; 3) Props.	The observations made found that the curriculum that had been set could be seen and was always a guide for every field implementer in carrying out their activities. The data obtained confirms that each stakeholder in this program has understood the established curriculum and is able to implement and adjust the curriculum according to field conditions where the KKDN program is implemented.
I-5	Supervisor/ Lecturer	Have a competency diploma in accordance with the area of skills and material being taught as evidenced by a relevant competency certificate/diploma and able to carry out learning	Documentation found that in every activity of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) program always involves a supervisor who has competence in accordance with the object of the implementation of the Domestic Field Study (KKDN). The selected lecturers are given an assignment letter issued by the Chancellor of the National Defense University. The data obtained confirms that each selection of lecturers is determined by the leadership of the Study Program by considering the competencies and skills required by the object of the implementation of the Domestic Field Studyprogram (KKDN).
I-6	Resource persons	Have a competency diploma in accordance with the area of skills and material being taught as evidenced by a relevant competency certificate/diploma and able to carry out learning	Documentation found that in every KKDN activity it always involves supervisors and resource persons who have competencies that are in accordance with the object of the implementation of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) program. The selected supervisors and resource persons are given a letter of assignment issued by the UNHAN record. Interview results confirms that each supervisor and resource person involved, apart from being given a Rector's Decree, is also required to provide material and guide students according to the chosen object.
I-7	Organizer	Have a competency diploma in accordance with the area of skills and material being taught as evidenced by a relevant competency certificate/diploma and able to carry out learning	Documentation in the form of activity reports shows that every year, the implementation of the Domestic Field Studyprogram (KKDN) involves organizers who are responsible for the preparation and preparation of administration and logistics related to this activity. Interview results shows that the organizers are determined through the Rector's Decree every year and they are selected through a fair and transparent mechanism.
I-8	Participants	Have a competency diploma in accordance with the area of skills and material being taught as evidenced by a relevant competency certificate/diploma and able to carry out learning	Activity report shows that the activity participants are students who meet administrative requirements. The results of the interview showed that each participant filled out their study plan which included the Field Study (KK) courses which included the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) program.
I-9	Facilities and Infrastructure	All facilities and infrastructure required is available during the implementation of the activity.	The document shows that the implementation of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) program has prepared the necessary facilities and infrastructure. Interviews with the responsible division, namely the administration and logistics division, confirmed that the preparation of facilities and infrastructure for the Domestic Work Lecture (KKDN) program was their responsibility and had been prepared very well and measurably.
I-10	Monitoring and	There exists a plan to implement monitoring	The results of the supervision and inspection document fully explain that the supervision and inspection process

	Evaluation Mechanism	and evaluation	is carried out comprehensively. The results of the observations explain that the supervision and inspection are carried out comprehensively Interview results shows that monitoring and evaluation has been implemented according to plan.
I-11	Budget and Financial Plan	A budget and financial plan exists to support the implementation of the plan	Documentation shows that the budget and financing are adjusted to the ceiling in the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBN) and changes every year according to the location of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) where there is an allocation in the form of transportation and accommodation that adjusts the location of this program. Interview results shows that the budgeting process is carried out every fiscal year set by the government and UNHAN is based on the budget set by the Ministry of Defense.

Process Evaluation

Process evaluation is an evaluation process which includes how the program is run, monitored, developed, and also given input for the future. In the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) program, the evaluation of the components of the process includes the implementation of the KKDN, the implementation of management, the implementation of learning, the implementation of monitoring and evaluation and reports on program implementation. Table 3 depicts the results of Process Evaluation phase.

Table 3. Process Phase Research Results

Code	Aspect	Results
P1-1	Program Implementation	Documentation in the form of activity reports shows that every year, the implementation of the Domestic Field Studyprogram (KKDN) is carried out in different places adjusted to the theme taken by students and determined by UNHAN.
P1-2	Learning Implementation	The document shows that the mentoring process is carried out through guidance books carried out by students to their respective lecturers according to the theme they take and in accordance with the lecturer who handles the student. The results of field observations found that the interaction of students with supervisors in the process and implementation was carried out through several methods including seminars, focus group discussions and direct mentoring conducted by students.
P1-3	Monitoring and Evaluation	The implementation of supervision and inspection is also carried out in a professional and comprehensive manner so that the results of the supervision and inspection are credible and are also carried out through and using the mechanisms that have been prepared.
P1-4	Program Implementation Report	There is a program implementation report document made by each faculty with the same report structure in each faculty. The report is then submitted to the Chancellor as study material in the implementation of further activities. Interviews conducted with all persons in charge of activities in each faculty explained that they were required to make a report on the implementation of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) program no later than two weeks after the activity was completed using the format provided.
P1-5	Implementation Process	The process of implementing the Domestic Field Study(TKDN) program can be known and proven by many documents starting from planning activities, implementing activities and also activity reports. The results of field observations found that the implementation of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) program was carried out alternately every year depending on the object of the implementation of this program. Interviews with all parties involved in the implementation of this activity clearly show that the implementation of the Domestic Field Study(KKDN) program involves those who are indeed involved and appointed as persons in charge and other positions.

Product Evaluation

Product component evaluation is an evaluation process which includes the benefits of the program (impacts), effectiveness (effectiveness), can be implemented or transferred (transferability), can be carried out continuously (sustainability) and can be adjusted (adjustment). Table 4 shows the research results of the Product Evaluation phase

Table 4. Product Phase Research Results

P2-1	Program Output	Documentation shows that both soft skills and hard skills this program is very useful for students. For soft skills, students are better able to have responsibilities as evidenced by the timeliness in making reports on activities that are their respective responsibilities. Meanwhile, his hard skills are proven by the number of articles published in scientific journals according to the target. Interviews conducted with students participating in the program confirmed that they had a better understanding of the field conditions they experienced with the existing dynamics
P2-2	Outcomes	Documentation in the form of tracer studies shows that UNHAN graduates have good careers after they finish studying in the post-graduate program. This also explains that the domestic work course program has a very good impact on improving the competence of its graduates. Interviews with students conducted with graduates explained that they felt that the Domestic Field Study program had a very good contribution to their career journey because they increasingly had greater responsibility and empathy.
P2-3	Learning Outcomes	Documentation in the form of curriculum standards and the determination of graduate competency standards includes the Domestic Field Study as one of the pillars of the competence of graduates of UNHAN students
P2-4	Side Results	Interviews with all program participants showed that the KKDN program had a very significant impact in the form of 1) Increasing Confidence and 2) Commitment to the Profession for UNHAN students.
P1-10	Institution Capacity Development	Interviews with all stakeholders showed that the KKDN program had an impact in the form of 1) Improving the Quality of Research and Community Service and 2) Curriculum Quality.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusions

Analysis of the context component is that of all sub-components, the Domestic Field Study (KKDN) program has fulfilled the need for a demand-based program because the current policy requires universities to make more contributions to the community, one of which is through community service.

This study concludes that from the context evaluation component, the Domestic Field Study (KKDN) program has been supported with the right concept of thinking. In the long term this program can slowly be pushed to be more comprehensive with a longer time and more objects that are used as locations.

Based on the overall evaluation of the input components, the researcher can conclude that in general this component has been running well and in accordance with the established evaluation criteria. All elements meet the specified requirements.

In general, the conclusion from the evaluation of the process components went well even though there were suggestions for improvement that must be developed in the implementation of the KKDN in the years ahead by adopting the challenges of higher education going forward.

One of the most crucial things in the Domestic Field Study (KKDN) program is the output and impact of this program.

The output of this activity is the increasing number of scientific publications as a tangible result of the implementation. One of the measures is how they can return to their respective institutions and be able to make a positive contribution to their work environment. Of the other sub-components, namely the by-products obtained from this study, which show that self-confidence and commitment to the profession have developed. Meanwhile, the by-product in the form of institutional capacity building can be seen from how UNHAN continuously improves the quality of research and community service.

Recommendation

From the results of the evaluation of all evaluation components which include context components, inputs, processes and products, the researcher provides recommendations that will be useful if this program is run in the future:

1. The Domestic Field Study Program (KKDN) is still very feasible to be continued with some improvements, considering the many benefits obtained by the community who are the object of implementation as well as for students because they can compare the reality in the field with the theory they have received during college.
2. This Domestic Field Study Program (KKDN) needs to be more adapted to the latest regulations issued by the Ministry of Education and Culture where the Domestic Work Program (KKDN) can adopt the Merdeka Campus – Merdeka Learning program by increasing the duration of implementation which was previously only carried out for 1 (one) week can be extended to 1 (one) month and increase credits from 1 credit to 4 credits by making more comprehensive guidelines.
3. The Domestic Field Study Program (KKDN) requires a more in-depth study, especially in the selection of implementation objects based on very urgent factual conditions which may change from the initial planning due to the dynamics that occur in the territory of Indonesia. This is of course possible if there is flexibility in budgeting.
4. The output of activities in the form of scientific publications and or book publications with the theme of the object of research should be more focused because the publication history is unknown. The trick is to send research articles along with activity reports so that LPPM can verify.
5. Learning outcomes need to be more concreted by making appropriate indicators and measuring tools so that learning outcomes are not only measured by the success of the implementation but also by the impact resulting from the implementation of this program.
6. In order to be more measurable, UNHAN needs to conduct earlier and current studies related to security conditions or problems that arise and may arise in locations that have the potential to be the place for the implementation of the Domestic Field Study Lecture program (KKDN).
7. UNHAN also needs to conduct further research on objects that have been used as locations for the implementation of the Domestic Work Lecture program (KKDN) to see the impact of the Domestic Field Study Program (KKDN) that has been implemented. By looking at the impact it can be ascertained that the selection of the object is correct.

References

- Ananda, R., & Rafida, T. (2017). *Pengantar Evaluasi Program Pendidikan*. Medan: Perdana Publishing.
- Anwas, O. M. (2011). Kuliah Kerja Nyata Tematik Pos Pemberdayaan Keluarga Sebagai Model Pengabdian Masyarakat Di Perguruan Tinggi. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan*, 17(5), 565-575. doi:10.24832/jpnk.v17i5.49
- Arikunto, S. (2009). *Dasar-Dasar Evaluasi Pendidikan*. Yogyakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Arikunto, S., & Jabar, C. S. (2018). *Evaluasi Program Pendidikan: Pedoman Teoretis Praktis Bagi Mahasiswa dan Praktisi Pendidikan*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Chen, H.-T. (2005). *Practical Program Evaluation: Assessing and Improving Planning*. California: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Darodjat, & M, W. (2015). Model Evaluasi Program Pendidikan. *Islamadina*, 1-28.
- Dočekal, V., & Dvořáková, M. (2015). Evaluation levels in education. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 174, 3743 – 3749. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.1108
- Fitzpatrick, J. L., Sanders, J. R., & Worthen, B. R. (2010). *Program Evaluation: Alternative Approaches and Practical Guidelines, 4th Edition*. Pearson.
- Mulyatiningsih, E. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Terapan Bidang Pendidikan*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Spaulding, D. T. (2013). *Program Evaluation in Practice: Core Concepts and Examples for Discussion and Analysis, 2nd Edition*. New York: Jossey-Bass.
- Stufflebeam, D. L. (2002). The CIPP Model for Evaluation. In D. L. Stufflebeam, G. F. Madaus, & T. Kellaghan, *Evaluation Models*. Kluwer Publishing .
- Stufflebeam, D. L., & Zhang, G. (2017). *The CIPP Evaluation Model: How to Evaluate for Improvement and Accountability*. New York, USA: The Guilford Press.
- Sudjana, D. (2006). *Evaluasi Program Pendidikan Luar Sekolah : untuk pendidikan nonformal dan pengembangan sumber daya manusia*. Bandung: Rosdakarya.
- Tayibnapis, F. Y. (2018). *Evaluasi program dan instrumen evaluasi untuk program pendidikan dan penelitian*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Wholey, J. S., Hatry, H. P., & Newcomer, K. E. (2010). *Handbook of Practical Program Evaluation*. San Fransisco, USA: Jossey-Bass.
- Widoyoko, E. P. (2016). *Evaluasi program pembelajaran : panduan praktis bagi pendidik dan calon pendidik*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.

Widyaputra, S. (2018). Pembelajaran Mahasiswa KKN Terintegrasi PPM Universitas Padjadjaran dalam Menyampaikan Prototipe Hasil Penelitian Program Academic Leadership Grant Kepada Masyarakat Pengguna dan Calon Pengguna. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 2(9). Retrieved from <https://jurnal.unpad.ac.id/pkm/article/view/20347>

Wirawan. (2016). *Evaluasi Teori, Model, Standar, Aplikasi*. Depok: Rajawali Pers.

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